

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

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EFFECT OF 1-PHENYL, 1,2-DICHLOROETHANE ON THE VOLUME CONSUMPTION OF BUTADIENE-NITRILE RUBBER ALLOY UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND STRESSES

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Abstract

Research has been conducted to study the effect of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane on the rheological properties of butadiene-nitrile rubber under the influence of different temperatures and stresses. The volume consumption of alloys of binary mixtures of butadiene-nitrile rubber with 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane under the conditions of temperature and stress was studied and the appropriate processing mode was determined. According to the analysis of the obtained results, the rheological properties of alloys of SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane mixtures are expedient to process the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in this binary mixture by taking 4-5 mass parts and at a temperature of 150 ° C. It was found that the effect of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane on SKN-40 butadiene-nitrile rubber takes different forms depending on different temperature and stress conditions. It was found that the effect of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane on SKN-40 butadiene-nitrile rubber takes different forms depending on different temperature and stress conditions. Butadiene-nitrile rubber is mixed with 2-10 m.p. k 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane to prepare binary mixtures, study their flow index, rheological properties under the influence of different temperatures and stresses, determine the optimal ratio, processing mode, vulcanization time to the requirements of operating conditions is the acquisition of a composite material that can respond.

Keywords: Butadiene-nitrile rubber, nitrile-butadiene rubber, 1-phenyl, 1,2-dichloroethane, binary compounds, alloy volume consumption, modification, elastomers, rheology, functional rubber, special purpose polymer, different temperatures and stresses.

Introduction

Prior to the preparation of rubber mixtures based on SKN-40 rubber and 1-phenyl, 1, -dichloroethane mixtures in the traditional processing of polymers and the study of the complex properties of their vulcanizates, binary mixtures of butadiene-nitrile rubber with 1-phenyl, 1,2-dichloroethane were prepared. The dependence of the volume consumption of alloys of SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane binary mixtures under the influence of different temperatures and stresses on the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in the mixture was studied [1-6]. It was determined that in the SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane binary mixture with the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane (2-6) masses part-mass portions (m.p or wt.%) in the mixture under (11.75 and 20.85) kg of weight, at a temperature of (100-120° C) the volume consumption of the alloy decreases, ie the structure of the rubber is cured, and when the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in the mixture is more than 6 m.p., the volume consumption of the alloy increases, ie destruction occurs. Studies have shown that 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane accelerates the vulcanization process. In the future, we will also consider the preparation of compositions based on SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane mixtures and their vulcanization process.

Development of modern industrial enterprises is due to the properties of polymer materials. Currently, many of them are not in accordance with multitasking polymers and compositional materials based on the growing consumer requirements in a number of cases[7-9]. Actually, using various modification methods of polymers to buy polymer materials that meet increased consumer requirements, effective ways to get valuable composition material based on the basis. The modern rubber industry requires a number of products, which meets the requirements of various exploitation conditions[10]. It requires the development and research of a new variable rubber recipe that differs from the operating and technological properties.

Experimental part

The purpose of this study was to study 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane butadiene-nitrile rubber at different temperatures (100; 120; 150 and 170° C) and loads (weight) (11.75; 20.85; 26.1 and 32.6 kg) under the influence of the tension created by its structure, properties, to study the effect of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane on the fluidity properties and finally on the properties of the composition based on butadiene-nitrile rubber. For this purpose, butadiene-nitrile rubber is mechanically modified in the micro laboratory two-roll mill at 40-60°C temperature with different mass portions 1-phenyl 1,2 dichloroethane (Table 1.)

Table 1.

Composition of SKN - 40/1- phenyl 1,2 - dichloroethane binary mixtures

No	Code of the mixture						
	Components	1Z	2Z	3Z	4Z	5Z	6Z
1	SKN - 40	100	100	100	100	100	100
2	1-phenyl 1,2 dichloroethane	-	2.0	4.0	6.0	8.0	10
Total		100	102	104	106	108	110

The flow rates of the alloys of the obtained binary mixtures were studied in the IRIT-5 device. The volume consumption of alloys of binary mixtures under the influence of the above-mentioned temperatures (100; 120; 150; 170 ° C) and loads (1st weight =11,75 kg, 2nd weight=20,85kg, 3rd weight= 26,1 kg, 4th

weight = 32,6 kg) is shown below, respectively. We show a table with the time (in seconds) spent on the flow of alloys from the 2 mm capillary under the influence of the above-mentioned temperatures and loads of binary mixtures (Table 2.).

Table 2.

SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane mixtures of binary alloys in the flow of time spent (in seconds)

Examples	100°C				120°C			
	Weights, kg				Weights, kg			
	11.75	20.85	26.1	32.6	11.75	20.85	26.1	32.6
1Z	255.10	59.82	35.21	20.85	85.60	22.75	13.82	7.16
2Z	95.75	28.16	20.75	9.85	42.75	12.65	8.16	4.25
3Z	82.60	24.62	18.69	8.52	31.95	10.85	6.70	3.20
4Z	73.65	21.70	16.20	7.12	22.18	8.25	4.75	2.70
5Z	61.47	18.65	14.10	5.98	18.75	6.90	3.25	1.98
6Z	52,18	15,90	12,17	3,65	15,54	4,95	2,35	1,15
Examples	150°C				170°C			
	Weights, kg				Weights, kg			
	11.75	20.85	26.1	32.6	11.75	20.85	26.1	32.6
1Z	42.54	12.6	8.12	6.05	32.10	7.82	5.44	3.60
2Z	20.75	7.25	4.12	2.98	58.40	39.82	26.70	23.75
3Z	18.20	6.17	3.05	1.90	59.20	50.12	46.48	41.75
4Z	16.12	5.85	2.04	1.80	64.75	59.75	50.15	44.02
5Z	14.20	4.12	1.80	1.12	66.20	60.18	40.15	20.85
6Z	12.75	3.02	1.08	0.90	50.75	41.62	36.15	17.80

$G_1=11.75\text{kg}$, $G_2=20.85\text{kg}$, $G_3=26.1\text{kg}$, $G_4=32.6\text{kg}$ under the influence of stresses generated on the surface of the loads SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane binary system, the volume consumption of the alloy at different temperatures is calculated according to the following formula:

$$Q = \frac{S}{t} * \frac{\pi D_s^2}{4}$$

Here: Q- is the volume consumption of binary mixtures in compliant loads and temperatures $\text{sm}^3 * \text{sec}^{-1}$,

S- melt flow length cm,

t - the spent time for the alloy to flow along the S length,

D_s - cylindrical chamber with a diameter of the device, cm.

SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane mixture of binary alloys viscosity (volume waste) properties studied on the capillary viscometer. With the formation of the core polymer processing techniques (extrusion, casting under pressure, etc.) are being taken in the event of their viscous flow SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane binary mixtures of the above-mentioned different (complex) studied the deformation properties of the optimal conditions of flow conditions by selecting the

compositions on the basis of extrusion, injection molding products, manufacturing opportunities can be created by using the formation.

SKN-40 and 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane binary mixtures are drawn in equal amounts (at different temperatures) and placed in the cylinder (chamber) of the capillary viscometer and kept for 4 minutes to take the temperature of the chamber, then placed on the surface of the sample - stock. loads are placed (separately). Under the influence of these loads, the centers of gravity of macromolecules do not rotate relative to each other, and the flow continues due to irreversible deformation. Therefore, for the flow of the polymer alloy (for the displacement of macromolecules), the conformation of the macromolecules is changed by repelling the interactions between the macromolecules.

Results and its discussion

An analysis of the graphic curves (Figure 1-4.) (Q- volume consumption 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane dependence) based on the results of the research shows that the volume consumption of the curve increases with increasing of the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane at 100 and 120°C with the addition of all loads (Figure 1,2). At a temperature of 150 ° C, under the influence of loads of 11.75 and 20.85 kg, the volume consumption of the alloy of the mixture is relatively stable when the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in the

mixture is (2-6 m.p.) when the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane is more than 6 m.p., the volume consumption increases rapidly (Figure 3.).

This suggests that when 4-6 m.p. 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane is present in the mixture, it interacts with butadiene-nitrile rubber, causing an increase in molecular weight by altering the macrostructure of the rubber, and the volume consumption of the alloy varies slightly, 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane when it is higher than 6m.p., it performs plasticizing properties with butadiene-nitrile rubber.

Under the influence of loads of 26.1 and 32.6 kg, the volume consumption of the alloy SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane increases monotonously and differs sharply from the volume consumption of the alloy under the influence of loads of 11.75 and 20.85 kg. This

suggests that SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane and its compositions can be processed under loads of 11.75 and 20.85 kg. When the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in the mixture SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane at 170 °C is 4-6 m.p., the volume consumption of the mixture alloy under the stress created by all loads is reduced to a minimum, the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane when it is more than 6 m.p., the volume consumption of the alloy increases sharply (Figure 4.).

This means that when the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in the mixture is 2-6 m.p., 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane interacts with butadiene-nitrile rubber and the mixture becomes highly elastic, 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane further increase exposure in the mixture accelerates the destruction process of the mixture.

Figure 1. Volume consumption of alloy of SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2 dichloroethane binary mixture at 100 o C temperature depends on the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in the mixture

Figure 2. Volume consumption of alloy of SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2 dichloroethane binary mixture at 120 o C temperature depends on the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in the mixture

Figure 3. Volume consumption of alloy of SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2 dichloroethane binary mixture at 150 o C temperature depends on the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in the mixture

Figure 4. Volume consumption of alloy of SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2 dichloroethane binary mixture at 150 o C temperature depends on the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in the mixture

Based on the results of the investigations, it can be concluded that the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in the SKN-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane mixture is 2-6 m.p. under the stress of loads of 11.75 and 20.85 kg and at a temperature of 150-155 ° C composite materials with increased resistance to aggressive environments can be obtained by processing.

References

- Han Heng, Wang Shijie, Ly Xiaoren, Zhang Bo, Zhang Yuzeng., Effect of oxidative surface modification on the mechanical properties of rubber based on nitrile butadiene rubber. Shenyang gongye daxue xuebao J Shenyang Univ. Technol. 2013. 35, № 6, P. 662-666.
- S.V. Gusev, D.S. Voropaev, K.V. Sukhareva et al., Mechanochemical modification of NBR in the presence of a chlorine-containing reagent. N. M. Emanuel RAS, Russian University of Economics. News of VolgGTU No. 5, 2020, P. 59-63.
- Babayeva M., Study of the rheological properties of triple ethylene-propylene rubber (SKEPT-60) modified with 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane and compositions based on them, Internauka nauchny zhurnal part 2, № 22 (56) Moscow, 2018, P.15-18
- Khaled F., El-Nemr, Effect of different curing systems on the mechanical and physico-chemical properties of NBR vulcanizates, Materials & Design, Vol.32, 2011, P. 3361-3369
- Shuai Li, Tong Liu, Lijie Wang & Zhaobo Wang., Dynamically Vulcanized NBR/EVE Blends Compatibilized by CPE., Journal of Macromolecular Science, Vol. 52, 2013, P. 13-21
- Yuan Fan, Ur Ryong Cho., Influence of the hybrid materials based on carbon nanotubes and tannic

acid on the rheological, thermal and mechanical performances of NBR composites Vol.40 , 2019,P.4510-4518

7. Nanying Ninga, Xiangyan Lia, Hongchi Tian et al., Unique microstructure of an oil resistant NBR/PP dynamically vulcanized thermoplastic elastomer., RSC Advances, Vol. 7, 2017, P. 5451–5458

8. Chuanhui Xu, Liming Fang, Yukun Chen., Reactive compatibilized PP/NBR blends by zinc dimethacrylate: Preparation, structure, and properties, Polymer Engineering & Science, Vol.54, 2014 P. 2321-2331

9. S.Khashirova, A. Zhansitov & A. Vindizheva., Influence of Phytonorman Eco-Oils Nature and Content on Processing of the Elastomeric Materials Based on Nitrile Butadiene Rubber Analysis., Key Engineering Materials, Vol.899, P. 752-758

10. Sh.M. Mamedov, A.A. Garibov, S.A. Rzaeva, F.I. Yadreev, O.V. Sigov., The Radiation Vulcanisation of HNBR., Elastomer and rubber journal 2015., Vol. 42, P. 7-10

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RHEOLOGY OF MIXTURES OF 1-PHENYL 1,2-DICHLOROETHANE WITH BUTADIENE-NITRILE RUBBER AND STUDY OF THE PROPERTIES OF THEIR COMPOSITIONS

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Abstract

In this scientific study, 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane and NBR-40 butadiene-nitrile rubber-based compounds resistant to aggressive environments were prepared. First, the rheology was studied by preparing binary mixtures with 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane and NBR-40, and the optimal amount and processing conditions required to contain 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane were determined. Second, vulcanizates based on a special recipe containing NBR-40 with 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane were obtained and their physical and mechanical properties were examined. It has been found that the addition of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane improves the physical and mechanical properties of a series of compounds.

Keywords: nitrile-butadiene rubber, 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane, rheology, modification, elastomers, infrared spectroscopy, physical and mechanical properties, functional rubber, special purpose polymer, polymer composites

Introduction

Butadiene-nitrile rubber is the main productive material for the production of rubber with high resistance to petroleum products and other aggressive media. The synthetic polymer is a product of the copolymerization of butadiene with acrylonitrile (ACN). The properties of the copolymer depend on the amount of ACN in the polymer, that is, the higher it is, the higher its resistance to oils, but the lower its elasticity.

Butadiene-nitrile rubber-based elastomeric materials are widely used in the oil industry for the production of sealants of various aggregates (such as seals, grommets etc.) operating in harsh conditions. Since the modification of butadiene-nitrile rubber (NBR) by means of compounds with different functional groups seems perspective, the structure of the butadiene-nitrile rubber is intentionally altered by the inclusion of chloride-containing compounds [1]. Such additives improve co-assimilation of polymers in the contact area between polymer phases and prevent phase separation [2].

Studies were carried out by including 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane, a functional group compound, in the composition based on butadiene-nitrile rubber [3]. First, the rheology of their binary mixtures was studied depending on the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane included in butadiene-nitrile rubber, and the optimal processing regime was determined [4]. Then, the degree of influence of the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in compositions based on NBR/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane on the properties of elasticity-strength, strength of metal bonds, etc. was studied.

Experimental part

In this study, a binary system was prepared by mechanically mixing different proportions of butadiene-nitrile rubber (NBR-40) with 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane on a micro laboratory two-roll mill at 40-50 °C for 5-8 minutes (Table 1). NBR-40 is a trademark of butadiene-nitrile rubber which contain nearly 40% of ACN.

Table 1.

Composition of NBR-40/1- phenyl 1,2 - dichloroethane binary mixtures by mass portions (m.p.)

No	Code of the mixture						
	Components	1Z	2Z	3Z	4Z	5Z	6Z
1	NBR-40	100	98	96	94	92	90
2	1-phenyl 1,2 dichloroethane	-	2.0	4.0	6.0	8.0	10
	Total	100	100	100	100	100	100